

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TOXICITY AND THE SACRED: LITERARY AND MISSIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES ON ETHICAL CONTAMINATION

Bogdan Andrei

Ph.D.,

Associated Prof., Faculty of Letters/ Faculty of Theology

University Oradea/University of West Timișoara

Oradea, Romania

410276

ORCID: 0009-0000-2295-0937

Abstract

Toxicity and the Sacred: Literary and Missiological Perspectives on Ethical Contamination, tries to deal with two major issues which really revolve around two spiritual and moral concepts of our society that is degrading over time and the belief of toxicity in religious places, ethics, and discourse. Nowadays the sacred and the profane are not as clear as they used to be. The paper argues that this is the case in the digital age when even the sacred is not considered sacred anymore. To illustrate the problem of guarding spiritual integrity, the paper refers to contemporary authors such as Marilynne Robinson and Jonathan Franzen. For instance, the author in the novel *Gilead* mentions spiritual resistance to societal decay and encourages readers to develop such traits. The author in the other novel *Purity* evaluates the ethical consequences of media culture. The segue is also done with social media's role in moral contamination where anonymity endorses hostility and if Lincoln in the *Bardo* wouldn't have been written, George Saunders wouldn't have had such a topic to explore. Furthermore, the argument is fortified by Zadie Smith's *Swing Time* and Colson Whitehead's *The Nickel Boys* which demonstrate that the diversities in identities and disunity in society are among many other factors contributing to the deterioration of the common life and the spiritual one. Through these literary perspectives, the paper shows that missiology has to deal with these issues by enabling ethical clarity and spiritual resilience, and offering a space for redemption in the midst of contamination.

Keywords: missiology, ethical boundaries, moral decay, contemporary literature, preservation modern cultural challenges.

Introduction

The term *toxic* is now almost everywhere in public discourse, and as a result, it has expanded its original biological meaning to cover a wide range of social, cultural, and moral phenomena. As per the Oxford English Dictionary, the word of the year 2018, the term indicates a growing awareness of how negativity penetrates life in the digital world, particularly. In her book *Gilead*, Marilynne Robinson addresses the problem of social toxicity which leads to subtle spiritual erosion and thus we can use moral filtration to understand this problem as both a societal and personal crisis. Similarly, Jonathan Franzen's *Purity* demonstrates how the digital environment, especially social media, is a breeding ground for destructive behaviours, anonymity, and ethical compromise due to the nature of these spaces. (Nadel, 2017: 62)

These platforms are, therefore, the breeding grounds of what can be called *digital toxicity*, where the hostility, division, and moral ambiguity are multiplied. This toxic atmosphere, as cited by George Saunders in his work, *Lincoln in the Bardo*, is not a simple reflection of the ethical dilemmas of individuals but rather it is a result of a collective moral decay. Digital toxicity has become a dominating phenomenon that has resulted in the blurring of the lines between public and private morality, hence making the ethical life in the contemporary society a much more complicated affair. Therefore, the idea of toxicity has developed and is now not

only associated with physical or environmental pollution but as such, has become a metaphor for the moral and spiritual contamination that is typical of modern life. (Franzen, 2011: 79)

Research methodology

In my article, I took a multidisciplinary approach, which included literary analysis, missiological theory, and ethical critique to study the concept of toxicity in sacred and secular contexts. The methodology is derived from both qualitative textual analysis and contextual theology, which examines the interaction between literature and missiological perspectives concerning the moral contamination of moral wrongs. By carrying out an exegesis of contemporary literary works, including *The Overstory* by Richard Powers, *Sing, Unburied, Sing* by Jesmyn Ward, and *Swing Time* by Zadie Smith, I analyzed the way the authors depict spiritual and ethical problems in a world that is both *toxic* culturally and ecologically. Thematic appropriateness to the issues of moral decay, resilience, and spiritual healing is the reason why these literary case studies were chosen to be discussed in the nuance range of contamination beyond its physical manifestation.

Moreover, the missiological framework that was utilized in the article is based on the study of ethical boundaries and spiritual integrity which was expressed in the key theological writings. I critically engaged with concepts of sacredness, moral purity, and ethical decay,

which I aligned with digital and social toxicity in contemporary society. I was able to analyze literature through a missiological perspective and thus I could interrogate the broader implications of toxicity on mission work and the preservation of sacred spaces, whereby theological insights were used to support the literary critique. This integrated methodology provides a wide-ranging view of how modern fiction and missiology mutually enlighten and disrupt each other in the common theme of ethical contamination.

I. Missiology in a toxic world: the challenge of spiritual integrity

Spiritual integrity of the Church Reflections in a world of digital farce The Church is the Church that is in oppressed morality and submissive to the digital toxicity, thus, the mission of the Church is burdened with a heavy cause, above all the fact of being the Church spiritual integrity. The idea of sacred spaces in the beginning was seen as something of refuge from the world and moral clarity. However, it is now the object of societal contamination. Missiology which is a theological discipline that aims to progress the Church's mission must face the ethical dilemmas that arise when moral pollution invades the sanctified places which are represented by the Church. Spiritual purity the way it is articulated in *Gilead* by Marilynne Robinson where faith and a world in moral disarray are in conflict is a literary representation of the missiological dilemma. In addition, Jonathan Franzen's *Purity* is a meditation on the ethical decay of both personal and societal levels which is a reflection of the unstable moral character of a toxic environment that is under the influence of digital and social media. (Caverly, 2020: 24)

Thus, the problem of missiology in such a world is not only the preservation of the sacred spaces but also the direct confrontation of the forces that threaten them. Sacred spaces, whether they be physical or metaphorical domains, are not immune from moral contamination that spreads through digital toxicity which is the cause of the proliferation of social media and the online platforms that are the channels for enmity, division, and ethical compromise. It is more than the problems of individual moral lapses; as George Saunders shows in *Lincoln in the Bardo*, the spiritual malfunction of disintegrated communities is the deeper struggle of keeping the moral purity of the whole as a collective. Consequently, the Church, amidst these complexities, becomes a model of spiritual resistance against the toxic influence of culture. Missiological ethics must be re-envisioned, not only as a defensive mechanism to preserve the sacred but as an active engagement with a world that is morally compromised. (Burn, 2008: 153)

It should be known that the consecration of spaces in churches, religious communities, or in-between people's hearts requires constant awareness against moral decay. Zadie Smith's *Swing Time* touches on the instabilities of identities and the ethical dilemmas that arise due to cultural relations, but still it emphasizes the need of remaining spiritual clarity in a world that is often too unclear in terms of right and wrong. It is a parallel to the missiological task of the labor of upholding the ethical standards in the environments where the sacred is under siege. Thus, the role of missiology is not merely

to point out the contamination but to seek a type of ethical engagement that goes beyond the divisions that the digital and societal toxicity have created. The Church's mission must, therefore, change in response to these realities, developing moral clarity and spiritual healing spaces that not only withstand the impact of moral pollution but also actively purify a world that is increasingly contaminated. (Green, 2015: 36)

II. Contemporary writers on spiritual contamination: lessons from literature

The study of the literary representation of spiritual degeneration in the modern world is vital for the comprehension of the ethical issues of modernity. The writers, such as Marilynne Robinson, Jonathan Franzen, and George Saunders, are dealing with the problems of moral decay, the disintegration of community, and the spiritual resilience. Therefore, they expose the destructive ways in which individual and collective ethics can be eroded in a toxic environment. Robinson's church of *Gilead* demonstrates to us the personal faith of an individual in the face of immorality; as in the story, Reverend John Ames is struggling with the challenge of keeping his spiritual integrity when the sacred gets threatened by doubt, suffering, and ethical compromise. Robinson displays the silent strength of spiritual resilience in Ames' inner struggles. The author states that, although contamination is everywhere, the sacredness of faith can be saved by reflection, humility, and a steadfastness to moral clarity. (Burn, 2019: 80)

However, it could be *Purity's* people or the community represented in *Grace in the Wake of Danger* who are the ones facing the digital/social pressures that are bombarding the characters. Nevertheless, the characters are dealing with the ethical crises on the individual and communal levels throughout many of Jonathan Franzen's works. The effect of the decision to ego check or not in a world like this gives Friedman characters to privacy and moral choices that decide if the world is still holding together or if it is falling apart. The story is about the collapse of modern communities, where the common values provided the ground for solidarity, the ethical ambiguity, and the technological mediation led to the disintegration. The tendency of spiritual pollution to get away from the individual and the common degradation of community and society is what moves the plot of Franzen. (Green, 2015: 163)

On the other hand, George Saunders, in debating spiritual contamination through the *Lincoln in the Bardo*, uncompromisingly points out the ethical dilemmas that a people encounter during episodes of moral and existential crisis. It is a novel narrating the ambivalence between life and death, where souls dwell in the so-called *bardo* limbo-state and are faced with moral dilemmas and unresolved issues blocking their way for salvation. This supernatural premise allows Saunders to study how both personal and social compromises through time have led to the spiritual residues which are very hard to wash away. Besides, he graphically portrays characters who are caught up between guilt, fear, and moral ambiguity, thus, he makes the complex nature of spiritual contamination in a world that often denies or even avoids the ethical dilemmas easy to understand. (Saunders, 2013: 52)

The thematic connection of spiritual decay broadens the scope of the story by showing that the spiritual degeneration phenomenon is not a stand-alone phenomenon, but it is multi-faceted and affects not only individuals but also societies and communities as a whole. Robinson's depiction of quiet opposition is a perfect juxtaposition to Franzen's portrayal of a disintegrating society while Saunders' ruminations on ethical conflicts highlight the long and deep effects of the ethical failures that are usually ignored. (Latham, 2022: 97)

III. Digital anonymity and moral decay: the role of Media in spiritual spaces

Digital anonymity puts the moral and spiritual spaces that we live in today through radical change. The ethical code that used to apply to the online space has been replaced by a remodelling of this space. Those actions which would be up for a moratorium in a face-to-face setting are now the result of the anonymity granted by the internet. Hence, a point is given where the decay of morals is permitted to develop without any interference. This issue is later rephrased nicely by Jonathan Franzen in his book *Purity*. In this, the character-driven story, we find out what it is like to live in a digital world where the boundaries between the public and the private, the ethical and the unethical become blurred. Ultimately, the main characters in Franzen's book, who are mainly doing online experiments, often find themselves in a moral dilemma. A situation in which the absence of accountability results in the loss of moral values takes place. The actions they take, which are motivated by the sense of invisibility that Internet gives them, expose the fact that digital anonymity not only undermines individual integrity but also erodes the whole moral fabric. (Max. 2012: 101)

Besides, the online toxicity concept covers not only some unfortunately harmful accidents like trolling or cyberbullying but also some other moral resolution's tacit dimensions. The very way in which a person can launch into an anonymous exchange of ideas and statements on social media platforms is an ethical line that is often crossed. George Saunders, in *Lincoln in the Bardo*, at the same time, undermines this idea by using his metaphor of souls in a spiritual limbo. Souls are those whose moral questions remain unresolved under the sun. One can say so, as the characters in the supernatural realm are in a stagnant moral status that looks like ethical paralysis, which is often the case in online interactions, where people are ready to be hostile or divisive without fear of the repercussions. However, the absence of these morals, which are reinforced by anonymity, causes the creation of a toxic digital milieu which not only is a harbour for these harmful practices but also it inhibits the personal responsibility which is essential for the maintaining of the spiritual integrity. (Powers, 2018: 29-30)

The role of the media in amplifying these issues is even more crucial, as the current media platforms facilitate the rapid dissemination of toxic behaviours and their penetration into the spiritual spaces that were once safeguarded as areas of ethical reflection is unavoidable. Marilynne Robinson's *Gilead* as a first and fore-

most approach to this, painting a world where confidentiality and spirituality are put forward against the digital world. In the story, the protagonist Reverend John Ames manifests a sequence of moral gifts like patience, humility, and ethical self-control that in online settings are not often available due to the immediate and anonymous culture of online sites. The one that is centered on spiritual resistance, *Gilead*, propagates a strong reminder that moral clarity is needed in a world that is often expected to adhere to quick judgment and superficial standards instead of thorough ethical engagement. (Garrard, 2021: 125)

IV. The Sacred and the Secular: navigating ethical contamination in modern mission work

The very intersection of the sacred and the secular in modern mission work gives rise to a serious challenge, particularly when ethical contamination that is due to the fragmentation of society and culture has to be dealt with. In Zadie Smith's *Swing Time*, for the sake of keeping differing cultural identities intact, the clash between two cultures that are initially different and incompatible is presented as a complex problem to be solved. The novel reveals the aspiration of the individual on the one hand, and cultural roots on the other hand, pointing out that individuals often find themselves in such a situation when two moral codes are in conflict. Caught between tradition along with its sacred ideals and modernity, its secular pressures, Smith's characters represent the ethical dilemmas that contemporary mission work faces when trying to bridge these divides. Missionaries, like the characters in *Swing Time*, have to manoeuvre through the drifting terrain of moral values as they come across communities whose worldviews are in conflict. This task not only requires a profound comprehension of the sacred but also a delicate handling of the ethical problems that are brought about by secular beliefs. (Clark, 2015: 136)

Colson Whitehead's *The Underground Railroad* similarly deals with the issue of social fractures and their effect on moral integrity as it depicts in a clear way the people who live in a world where ethical compromise is rampant. The novel, which narrates the story of enslaved people seeking freedom, serves as a vivid metaphor of the ways in which societal structures can become morally contaminated. Whitehead's heroes, compelled to face the cruel experience of a torn society, resisting the temptations of a morale aim being in a dearth of a justice, have hard time finding their moral position. It is in this light that the contemporary mission work should find ways of countering the uttering societal fractures that tend to interfere with the moral and spiritual unity of the communities they serve. The sacred represented in the struggle for justice and spiritual purity often clashes with the hard facts of a world marked by historical and cultural wounds. (Ward, 2017: 90)

With mission work in a more direct relationship with secular spaces, it is evident that the sacred and the secular are not as distinct as they may seem. The ethical purity contamination through the secular forces, regardless of the cultural fragmentation or the societal breakdown, becomes one of the critical obstacles for the missionaries aimed at upholding spiritual integrity.

Smith's and Whitehead's works bring to light the difficulty of steering through such ethical waters, where the sacred ideals of mission work have to be constantly redefined in relation to the complications of the modern world. The ongoing struggle between upholding ethical standards and being part of a world torn apart by cultural and societal contamination endows the changing role of mission work with contemporary significance. The sacred mission of spiritual renewal must, therefore, be within a secular world that is often resistant to ethical intervention, demanding the development of strategies that address both the spiritual and the ethical needs of the communities missionaries target. (Parham, 2020: 88)

This engagement with ethical contamination in modern mission work as reflected in the writing of Smith and Whitehead reveals the complex dynamics between the sacred and the secular and the necessity for a more adaptable and ethically responsive strategy to missionary work.

V. Literary visions of redemption: overcoming toxicity through spiritual healing

Redemption has a lot of different forms in the literature and these different forms can give a person a long way to go from overcoming toxicity to spiritual healing, a theme that has been convincingly confirmed by authors like Richard Powers and Jesmyn Ward. Thus, in *The Overstory*, Powers' weaving together of ecological and spiritual renewal creates a scenario where nature is no longer treated merely as a stage but as a key player in redemption. The novel investigates the fact that human detachment from the nature has led to the destruction of the environment as well as a moral decline which is the toxicity that touches even interpersonal relationships and societies. Powers' characters find redemption in their efforts to reconnect with nature, suggesting that the path to healing, both personal and collective, lies in recognizing the intrinsic value of the natural world and in adopting a more harmonious, spiritually grounded relationship with it. The vast story of the numerous characters and ecological plots shows that the healing from moral and environmental toxicity is not an immediate process, but rather it is the outcome of deep spiritual pondering and a reconsideration of the humanity's role within the larger ecosystem. (Franklin, 2018: 74)

Also, the correlation of Jesmyn Ward's *Sing, Unburied, Sing* with redemption and resiliency is invaluable as it imparts the message that people and communities can rise above the pollution of the toxic legacies of racism, poverty, and trauma. In a rural American South setting, the novel depicts the characters' lives as they try to heal from the intergenerational wounds inflicted by the systemic injustice. Ward's illustration of spiritual healing is profoundly anchored in the courage of her characters who may be stuck in the pollution of their environment but, nevertheless, look for redemption via family and connection to the spiritual world. The novel's spectral presences, the unresolved traumas of the past, stand for the toxic legacies that haunt both individuals and communities. Nevertheless, the act of remembrance and the quest for spiritual reconciliation empower Ward's characters to face these ghosts, thereby, illustrating the possibility for healing even

from the most obstinate forms of moral contamination. (Head, 2008: 151)

Both Powers and Ward assert that redemption is not a lonely act but rather a communal one and a process which requires a new relationship with the sacred, whether it is through the natural world or through ties with family and culture. *The Overstory* is the power of Powers that the green health of the planet and the spiritual vitality of humanity are interlinked and that ecological deterioration is spiritual deficiency at its core. At the same time, Ward's *Sing, Unburied, Sing* emphasizes the confrontation of the historical toxicity for the sake of personal and community redemption, thereby, spiritual healing often requiring the undying look into the past traumas. Regardless of the various contexts of their stories, Powers' ecological view and Ward's exploration of racial and familial wounds, both authors come to the common point of view that redemption, although difficult, is attainable when a person reconnects with the sacred and undergoes spiritual healing. (Whitehead, 2016: 18)

Hence, the literary images of redemption, as talked about by Powers and Ward, show that the overcoming of toxicity, be it ecological or social, demands a deep spiritual renewal. The authors suggest that healing is a multifaceted phenomenon, one that requires not just the recovery of personal integrity but the re-establishment of connections with nature, history, and community as well. (Hadella, 2020: 68)

Conclusion

The interrogation of the issue of toxicity in sacred and secular contexts, as illustrated in recent literature and missiological thought, opens up a complex interaction between ethical contamination and the potential of spiritual healing. Just like, Richard Powers, in *The Overstory*, and Jesmyn Ward, in *Sing, Unburied, Sing* provide very valuable thoughts on what can be done by individuals and societies when facing the almost unbearable decay of society and environment. These narratives show that through a return to spiritual integrity and a re-engagement with the sacred, whether that is through ecological stewardship or the unearthing of historical trauma, redemption is possible. On the other hand, in missiological contexts, the difficulties caused by moral contamination which are either through cultural fragmentation, the one that Zadie Smith depicted in her story *Swing Time*, or societal fractures, the one that Colson Whitehead explored in *The Underground Railroad* are the ones that should be a rethinking of how mission work can adapt to the fractured realities of the modern world.

As mission work has to be more and more secular, the issue of contamination comes up and the spiritual resilience becomes the main role, a way out of the ethical toxins that fill up both digital and real spaces. Either through literature's looking of the spiritual healing or the ethical issues nowadays missiology brought up, it is clear that the fight against toxicity needs a comprehensive approach that interconnects both moral and spiritual dimensions, thus, offering the vision of renewal that no one would have thought which goes beyond the sacred and the secular.

References

1. Burn, Stephen J. Jonathan Franzen at the End of Postmodernism. London: Continuum, 2018.
2. Caverly, Douglas. Marilynne Robinson's World: Words, Spirit, and Reform. Waco: Baylor University Press, 2020.
3. Clark, Timothy. Ecocriticism on the Edge: The Anthropocene as a Threshold Concept. London: Bloomsbury, 2015.
4. Franklin, H. Bruce. Prison Writing in 20th Century America. New York: Penguin, 2018.
5. Franzen, Jonathan. The Corrections. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2011.
6. Garrard, Greg. Ecocriticism. London: Routledge, 2021.
7. Green, Jeremy. Late Postmodernism: American Fiction at the Millennium. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015.
8. Hadella, Charlotte. Understanding Marilynne Robinson. Columbia: University of South Carolina Press, 2020.
9. Head, Dominic. Contemporary British Novelists: Zadie Smith. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2008.
10. Latham, Rob. George Saunders: Critical Essays. Baton Rouge: Louisiana State University Press, 2022.
11. Max, D.T. Every Love Story is a Ghost Story: A Life of David Foster Wallace. New York: Viking, 2012.
12. Nadel, Ira B. Critical Insights: Marilynne Robinson. Pasadena: Salem Press, 2017.
13. Parham, Marisa. Ghostly Matters in Jesmyn Ward's South: Essays on Trauma and Memory. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2020.
14. Powers, Richard. The Overstory. New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 2018.
15. Robinson, Marilynne. Gilead. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2004.
16. Robinson, Marilynne. When I Was a Child, I Read Books. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2012.
17. Saunders, George. Tenth of December. New York: Random House, 2013.
18. Smith, Zadie. Swing Time. New York: Penguin Press, 2016.
19. Tew, Philip. Zadie Smith. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010.
20. Ward, Jesmyn. Sing, Unburied, Sing. New York: Scribner, 2017.
21. Whitehead, Colson. The Underground Railroad. New York: Doubleday, 2016.